

DEVELOPMENT AND SENSORIAL EVALUATION OF FERMENTED GOLDEN APPLE SNAIL (*Pomacea canaliculata*) BAGOONG

Lyra Hycinth C. Lutan ¹ and Maria Cristina Lalaine M. Nerona, Ph.D. ²

¹*Gamu Agri-Fishery School, Department of Education, Isabela, Philippines*

²*Isabela State University-City of Ilagan Campus, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the development and sensorial evaluation of fermented golden apple snail (*Pomacea canaliculata*) bagoong. Employing a survey research method, sensory evaluation was conducted among children, teenagers, adults, and experts to assess acceptability based on color, aroma, taste, and texture. Laboratory analysis by the Department of Agriculture Region 02 determined nutritional values, while shelf-life observation spanned three months. Forty (40) evaluators from diverse backgrounds assessed finished products, utilizing a standardized scorecard and a 9-point Likert Scale. Findings revealed varying preferences across age groups, with Pinakbet and Binaggoongan recipes consistently garnering high acceptability scores. Significant differences in perception of bagoong in different recipes were noted among groups. Nutritional analysis indicates moderate crude protein, low fiber and fat content, high moisture, and relatively high ash content, suggesting beneficial nutritional characteristics. Shelf-life observation suggests approximately three months at room temperature. This research offers valuable insights into the sensory evaluation and nutritional attributes of fermented golden apple snail bagoong, potentially informing its utilization as a food product.

Keywords: *Golden Apple Snail, fermentation, sensory evaluation, bagoong, shelf life*

INTRODUCTION

The consumption of fermented foods has been deeply ingrained in the dietary habits of various cultures worldwide for centuries, serving not only as a means of food preservation but also as a reflection of cultural identity and tradition. In the Philippines, fermented foods such as bagoong, pinakbet, and *burong isda* hold a special place in culinary traditions, showcasing the rich diversity of flavors and techniques inherent in Filipino cuisine (Ong, 2016). Similarly, neighboring countries like Thailand, Vietnam, Malaysia, and Indonesia boast their unique variations of fermented seafood products, each contributing to the vibrant tapestry of Southeast Asian gastronomy (Monteclaro, 2019).

Historically, the fermentation of fish products has been a common practice across many societies, with salt fermentation emerging as a particularly effective method for preserving fish due to its ability to reduce moisture content and inhibit bacterial growth (Olympia, 1992). This technique has played a crucial role in sustaining communities during periods of fish scarcity, ensuring a reliable protein source even in challenging environmental conditions. The enduring cultural and economic significance of fermented fish products is evident in the historical trade of delicacies such as garum in ancient Greece and Rome, highlighting the integral role of these foods in global culinary heritage (Beddows, 1985).

Despite their cultural importance, traditional methods of fermenting fish and other foods often require significant manual labor and lack modern infrastructure for large-scale production (Olympia, 1992). However, recent advancements in food science and technology have opened new avenues for innovation in fermentation processes, offering opportunities to streamline production methods and enhance product quality while preserving traditional flavors and techniques (Steinkraus, 1995). Collaborative efforts between local communities, researchers, and government agencies can play a vital role in revitalizing traditional food practices while ensuring their sustainability and economic viability in the modern age (Gálvez, 2010).

The proposal to explore the use of Golden Apple Snails as a raw material for fermented bagoong represents a novel approach to addressing both agricultural and culinary challenges in the Philippines. Golden snails, while traditionally considered pests due to their detrimental impact on rice crops, possess untapped potential as a valuable protein source and culinary ingredient (Hayes et al., 2008). By repurposing these snails for food production, rice farmers can not only mitigate crop damage and yield losses but also diversify their income streams and contribute to the development of innovative, value-added food products (Martínez-González et al., 2019).

In summary, the systematic exploration of fermentation processes, coupled with interdisciplinary collaboration and community engagement, holds immense promise for promoting the sustainable utilization of natural resources and fostering resilience in local

food systems. By preserving and adapting traditional food practices to meet contemporary challenges, societies can uphold cultural heritage, support economic development, and ensure food security for future generations.

Hence, this study aimed to explore the development of bagoong from fermented golden apple snails, particularly determining the procedure, the sensorial acceptability of the developed product, its nutritional value, and shelf life.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop fermented golden apple snail bagoong. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the process of making golden apple snail bagoong?
2. What is the level of acceptability of golden apple snail bagoong across groups of respondents in terms of:
 - a. color
 - b. aroma
 - c. taste
 - d. texture
3. What is the level of acceptability of golden apple snail bagoong as used in two different recipes in terms of:
 - a. appearance
 - b. aroma
 - c. taste
4. Is there a significant difference in the general acceptability of golden apple snail bagoong as used in two different recipes across different groups?
 - a. children
 - b. teenagers
 - c. adult
 - d. food experts
5. What is the nutritional value of golden apple snail *bagoong*?
6. What is the shelf-life of golden apple snail bagoong at room temperature?

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the survey research method was employed to determine the level of acceptability of the Golden Apple Snail Bagoong in terms of color, aroma, taste, and texture. The general acceptability of the fermented bagoong was evaluated through sensory evaluation by children, teenagers, adults, and experts. Furthermore, the nutritional values of the developed Golden Apple Snail products were determined through a laboratory test conducted by the Integrated Laboratory Division of the Department of Agriculture (DA) Region 02. The researcher conducted direct observation to determine the shelf life of the bagoong product stored at room temperature.

Materials

The tools, utensils, and ingredients used in conducting the study are shown in the tables below.

Table 1. Tools used in the conduct of the study.

Preparatory Tools	Cooking Tools	Cutting Tools	Mixing Tools	Measuring Tools	Equipment
Basin Strainer Utility Tray Colander Glass Jars	Ladle Frying Pan Casserole	Knife Chopping board	Mixing Bowls	Measuring cups Weighing Scale Measuring spoons	Gas Range

Ingredients

Table 2. Proportion of ingredients used in the preparation and brining of snail meat

Brine Solution

Ingredients	Measurements
Golden apple snail meat	2 cups
Salt	1 cup
Water	3 cups

Table 3. Proportion of ingredients used in the golden apple snail meat.

Ingredients	Measurements
Golden apple snail meat	300 grams
Salt	75 grams

Table 4. List of ingredients of Pinakbet and Pork Binagoongan dishes with Golden Apple Snail Bagoong.

	Pinakbet		Pork Binagoongan
¼ kg	Pork	1 kg	Pork Belly
12 cloves	Garlic	12 cloves	Garlic
2 pcs	Ginger	2.5 cup	Vegetable Oil
5 pcs	Onion	5 pcs	Onion
¼ cup	Cooking Oil	¼ cup	Cooking Oil
¼ kg	Green Finger Chili	5 pcs	Tomato
½ kg	Eggplant	¼ kg	Green Finger Chili
½ kg	Lady Finger	¼ cup	Golden Apple Snail bagoong
¼ kg	Tomato	7.5 cups	Water
1 pc	Squash	3 T	Brown Sugar
1 bundle	String Beans		
¼ kg	Bitter Gourd		
¼ cup	Golden Apple Snail bagoong		

Developmental Procedure

To perform the research properly, the researcher followed carefully and consistently the flowchart of procedures for producing golden apple snail bagoong as presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Flow Diagram of Making Golden Apple Snail Bagoong

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission to conduct the study through sensory evaluation was requested from the respondents, consisting of children, teenagers, adults, and experts. After permission

was granted, the administration of the sensory evaluation form followed. Directions concerning the accomplishment of the questionnaires were discussed by the researcher with the evaluators personally. Copies of the checklist forms were retrieved after being completed by the respondents.

The Department of Agriculture Region 02 through its Integrated Laboratory Division performed a chemical laboratory analysis on the Golden Apple Snail Bagoong to determine its nutritional value. In addition, to determine the shelf life of the food products, the observation method was used to check on the changes in the color, aroma, taste, and texture of the fermented Golden Apple Snail bagoong. The observation ran for three months.

Sensory Evaluation

The finished products underwent a sensory evaluation, which involved forty (40) evaluators from various backgrounds: ten children, ten teenagers, ten adults, and ten food experts from Gamu Agri-Fishery School, Linglingay, Gamu, Isabela and TESDA – ISAT, Ilagan City, Isabela. These evaluators were selected randomly and briefed on the evaluation criteria using a standardized scorecard. The samples were presented on a table for assessment.

During the evaluation, the focus was on different recipes utilizing golden apple snail bagoong. Evaluators were instructed to assess the taste, smell, texture, appearance, and overall acceptability of the bagoong. Data on these parameters were collected and subsequently decoded for statistical analysis.

For data collection, a quantitative approach was adopted using a score sheet. Evaluators rated the acceptability of golden apple snail bagoong on a 9-point Likert Scale, where responses were solicited regarding taste, smell, texture, and appearance.

Table 5. 9-Point Hedonic Scale on sensory evaluation of golden apple snail bagoong

Numerical Value	Numerical Rating	Description
9	8.12-9.00	I like extremely
8	7.23-8.11	I like very much
7	6.34-7.22	I like moderately
6	5.45-6.33	I like slightly
5	4.56-5.44	Neither like nor dislike
4	3.67-4.55	I dislike slightly
3	2.78-3.66	I dislike moderately
2	1.89-2.77	I dislike very much
1	1.00-1.88	I dislike extremely

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Product Development

The development of Golden Apple Snail bagoong involved a meticulous process comprising several stages. It began with the harvesting of Golden Apple Snails, followed by thorough washing to eliminate any soil or debris adhering to the snails. The snails were then carefully selected, with empty shells, smaller snails, and those with shell damage being removed.

Following selection, the snails underwent soaking, likely for tenderization or preparation for subsequent processing steps. Shucking followed, delicately extracting the meat from its shell. The shucked meat was then soaked in a brine solution, serving various purposes such as flavor enhancement and preservation. Once soaked, excess liquid was drained, preparing the meat for the salting phase, a critical step contributing to both flavor development and preservation.

Finally, the bagoong was carefully packaged, ensuring its quality and readiness for distribution and consumption. Throughout each stage, meticulous observation and analysis informed the refinement of the Golden Apple Snail bagoong, ultimately culminating in a product tailored for utilization in popular recipes such as pinakbet and pork binagoongan.

Figure 2. Harvesting Golden Apple Snails at a pond

Level of Acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong in terms of Color, Aroma, Taste, and Texture

Table 6. Level of Acceptability of Golden Snail bagoong across groups of respondents

Children			
Evaluation Criteria	Mean	Sd	Description
Color	6.20	0.422	I like slightly
Aroma	5.00	2.211	I neither like nor dislike
Taste	6.60	2.171	I like moderately
Texture	7.40	0.699	I like it very much
Overall Mean	6.30	1.772	I like slightly
Teenagers			
Evaluation Criteria	Mean	Sd	Description
Color	6.50	2.014	I like moderately
Aroma	4.80	2.150	I neither like nor dislike
Taste	5.80	2.394	I like slightly
Texture	7.00	1.155	I like moderately
Overall Mean	6.025	2.082	I like slightly
Adults			
Evaluation Criteria	Mean	Sd	Description
Color	7.00	2.00	I like moderately
Aroma	7.00	1.826	I like moderately
Taste	8.00	0.943	I like it very much
Texture	7.70	0.675	I like it very much
Overall Mean	7.425	1.483	I like it very much
Experts			
Evaluation Criteria	Mean	Sd	Description
Color	6.90	1.449	I like moderately

Aroma	7.20	2.044	I like moderately
Taste	6.60	1.897	I like moderately
Texture	7.20	1.033	I like moderately
Overall Mean	6.975	1.609	I like moderately

The table reveals the level of acceptability of Golden Snail bagoong in terms of color, aroma, taste, and texture.

As can be gleaned from the table, in terms of *color*, data suggests that among the respondents, the adult gave the Golden Apple Snail with the highest mean weight of 7.00 described as “*I like it moderately*” while among the children like the “**color**” slightly with a mean of 6.20.

In terms of *aroma*, the Children indicated a neutral stance, neither liking nor disliking the aroma with a mean of 5.00. The Teenagers expressed a slightly lower liking for the aroma having a mean of 4.80. On the other hand, both Adults and Experts moderately liked the aroma with a mean of 7.00 and 7.20, respectively.

As to the *taste* of Golden Apple Snail, the Children and Experts both liked the taste moderately with a mean of 6.60. Teenagers showed slightly low preference, liking it only slightly with a mean of 5.80. Lastly, the adults highly appreciate the taste rating it with a mean of 8.00 which means that they like the taste very much.

Concerning *texture*, across all age groups, the texture was well received, with the highest liking from the adults with a mean of 7.70.

Based on the findings, the data suggests that adults generally have a higher preference for Golden Apple Snail, especially in terms of color, taste, and texture. Children and teenagers showed slightly lower preferences, with teenagers having a slightly lower liking for aroma and taste. Experts generally shared preferences similar to adults, particularly in aroma and taste. Overall, Golden Apple Snail seems to be well-received in terms of texture across all age groups.

General Acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong across Age Groups

Table 7. General Acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong across Age Groups

Respondents	Mean	Sd	Description
Children	6.30	1.772	I like moderately
Teenagers	6.025	2.082	I like slightly
Adults	7.425	1.483	I like very much
Experts	6.975	1.609	I like moderately

Overall Mean	6.681		I like moderately
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The table shows the general level of acceptability of the Golden Apple Snail across age groups.

Adults had the highest mean score, with a mean = 7.425 and Sd = 1.483 suggesting that they like Golden Apple Snail Bagoong *very much*. The lower standard deviation indicates more consistent preferences within the adult age group. On the other hand, teenagers expressed a slightly lower liking for Golden Apple Snail Bagoong with a mean = 6.025 with Sd = 2.082 showing that they like the Golden apple snail slightly, and there is also a higher level of variability in their preferences, as indicated by the higher standard deviation.

The overall mean across all age groups is 6.681, indicating a moderate level of liking for Golden Apple Snail Bagoong on average. Overall, adults seem to have the highest liking for Golden Apple Snail Bagoong, while teenagers have a slightly lower liking. Children express a moderate liking, and experts' preferences fall between teenagers and adults. The overall mean suggests a moderate level of acceptability across all age groups. Based on the given data, it appears that the general acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong varies across different age groups.

Level of Acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong as Used in Two Different Recipes

Table 8 presents the level of acceptability of Golden Snail Bagoong in two different recipes, Pinakbet and Binaggoongan. The evaluation criteria include Appearance, Aroma, Taste, and Overall Mean for each recipe across different age groups: Children, Teenagers, Adults, and Experts.

Table 8. Level of Acceptability of Golden Snail Bagoong as Used in Two Recipes

Pinakbet								
Evaluation Criteria	Mean Children	Description	Mean Teenagers	Description	Mean Adults	Description	Mean Experts	Description
Appearance	8.60	I like extremely	7.80	I like very much	8.60	I like it extremely	8.20	I like extremely
Aroma	8.30	I like extremely	7.80	I like very much	8.30	I like it extremely	8.20	I like extremely
Taste	8.70	I like extremely	8.30	I like extremely	8.30	I like extremely	8.10	I like very much
Overall Mean	8.533	I like extremely	7.967	I like very much	8.40	I like it extremely	8.167	I like it extremely
Binaggoongan								

Evaluation Criteria	Mean Children	Description	Mean Teenagers	Description	Mean Adults	Description	Mean Experts	Description
Appearance	8.30	I like extremely	7.50	I like very much	8.30	I like extremely	8.20	I like extremely
Aroma	8.50	I like extremely	7.50	I like very much	8.40	I like extremely	8.40	I like extremely
Taste	8.50	I like extremely	7.60	I like very much	8.70	I like extremely	8.60	I like extremely
Overall Mean	8.433	I like extremely	7.533	I like very much	8.467	I like extremely	8.40	I like extremely

Concerning Appearance, all groups, including Children, Teenagers, Adults, and Experts, express an extremely high liking for the appearance of Golden Snail Bagoong in Pinakbet. Similar to appearance, all groups showed an extremely high liking for the aroma in Pinakbet. Also, in terms of Taste, all groups indicate an extremely high liking for the taste of Golden Snail Bagoong in Pinakbet. This implies that the Golden Apple Snail Bagoong when used in pinakbet is consistently high across all age groups indicating an extremely high level of acceptability.

In the same manner, data show that when the golden Apple Snail Bagoong was used in the dish Binaggoongan, in terms of Appearance, all groups, including Children, Teenagers, Adults, and Experts, expressed a high liking for the appearance of the Golden Snail Bagoong in Binaggoongan. Also, similar to appearance, all groups show a high liking for the aroma of Binaggoongan. As to the taste, all groups indicate an extremely high liking for the taste of Golden Snail Bagoong in Binaggoongan. This suggests that the overall mean for Binaggoongan is consistently high across all age groups, indicating a very high level of acceptability.

In summary, Golden Snail Bagoong is extremely well-received across all age groups for both Pinakbet and Binaggoongan. The highest liking is consistently observed in the categories of Taste and Appearance. Experts generally rate the acceptability slightly higher, but all age groups express a very high level of liking.

Comparison in the General Acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong as Used in Two Different Recipes across Different Groups of Respondents

Table 9. Comparison between the General Acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong as Used in two Different Recipes across Different Groups of Respondents

Respondents	F-Value	ρ -Value	Decision	Remarks
Pinakbet	4.722	0.0352	H_0 is not Accepted	Significant

Binaggoongan	24.389	0.0002	H ₀ is not Accepted	Significant
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The findings of a comparison between the general acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong used in various menus across various respondent groups are shown in the table, with a particular emphasis on two dishes: *pinakbet* and *binaggoongan*. Each dish's F-value and p-value are given.

About Pinakbet, the F-value of 4.722 shows variance in the overall acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong among various groups. The p-value of 0.0352 is below the typical significance threshold of 0.05. This implies that the groups of respondents had very different opinions about how acceptable Golden Apple Snail Bagoong is in Pinakbet. It follows that there are significant variations in how each group perceives Pinakbet with Golden Apple Snail Bagoong since the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected.

The F-value of 24.389 shows a greater variance in acceptability among groups in the setting of Binaggoongan, which is much higher than that of *Pinakbet*. The notion that there are notable variations in the acceptance of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong in *Binaggoongan* among the respondent groups is supported by the p-value of 0.0002, which is very significant. Rejecting the null hypothesis (H₀) in this instance strongly implies that there are notable differences in the perceptions of Binaggoongan and Golden Apple Snail Bagoong among other groups.

The analysis reveals that there are substantial variances in respondents' overall acceptability of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong, particularly when it comes to Binaggoongan, where these differences are more pronounced. Understanding customer preferences and making necessary adjustments to the use of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong in these meals could be greatly aided by these findings.

Nutritional Value of the Golden Apple Snail Bagoong

Table 10. The Chemical and Nutritional Value of the Golden Apple Snail Bagoong

Sample Description	Crude Protein	Crude Fiber	Crude Fat	Moisture	Ash	Total Protein
Golden Apple Snail Bagoong	12.27	0.20	0.43	59.95	24.67	1%

The provided information presents the nutritional content (in terms of crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat, moisture, and ash) of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong.

As to its nutritional content, the product contains 12.27 percent Crude Protein. This is a *moderate level of protein*, which may be considered favorable for those looking to include protein in their diet and making it a reasonable source of protein for individuals

seeking to include this nutrient in their diet. This can be particularly beneficial for those who may be looking for alternative protein sources, such as individuals with dietary restrictions or preferences. Also, the bagoong contains 0.20 percent of Crude Fiber. This means that low fiber content suggests that the bagoong may not contribute significantly to dietary fiber intake. This aspect of the nutritional profile could make the bagoong suitable for those prioritizing low-fat food choices, such as individuals managing weight or cardiovascular health

A Crude Fat of 0.43 percent is found in the bagoong. This shows that the low-fat content might appeal to those aiming for a low-fat diet. In addition, the Bagoong has a moisture content of 59.95 percent. The high moisture content indicates that the bagoong has a substantial water content. The ash content, which is 24.67 percent, is relatively high, suggesting the presence of minerals. While the specific minerals are not detailed, a higher ash content can indicate the presence of essential minerals. This may contribute positively to the overall nutritional value of the bagoong.

Lastly, the 1 percent total protein content in Golden Apple Snail Bagoong suggests a moderate contribution to dietary protein. Its role in culinary applications and overall nutrient balance should be considered, and individuals with specific protein requirements may choose to incorporate additional protein sources into their diet. As with any food item, context, individual dietary goals, and preferences play a key role in the interpretation of nutritional content.

The nutritional analysis indicates that Golden Apple Snail Bagoong can be a moderate source of protein with low levels of fiber and fat. Its high moisture content contributes to its overall texture, and the elevated ash content suggests potential mineral content. Understanding these nutritional aspects allows consumers to make informed choices based on their dietary preferences and health goals.

Shelf Life of Golden Apple Snail Bagoong stored at Room Temperature

The shelf life of golden apple snail bagoong, when stored at room temperature, appears to be approximately three months based on the observations provided. Initially, during the first week of fermentation, the bagoong maintains its quality, exhibiting a consistent appearance, color, and texture without any signs of spoilage or molds. This pattern continues into the second and third weeks, with no observable deterioration. By the fourth week, slight changes in color towards brownish hues are noted, but spoilage and molds remain absent.

However, by the second month, noticeable alterations in color and aroma occur, with the liquid becoming more brownish and emitting a stronger smell reminiscent of fish paste. Despite these changes, there are still no signs of spoilage, molds, or foul odor. By the third month, the bagoong is fully fermented, resembling fish paste both in smell and appearance, yet maintains its integrity without any indications of spoilage. Beyond this point, the bagoong may still be edible, but taste and quality may be affected by the advanced stage of fermentation.

Therefore, for optimal quality, it is advisable to consume the golden apple snail bagoong within the first three months of fermentation when stored at room temperature.

Figure 3. The Finished Product (Fermented Golden Apple Snail Bagoong)

Conclusions

Based on the comprehensive findings of the study, several key conclusions can be drawn. Firstly, there are discernible differences in the preferences for golden apple snail bagoong among various age groups, with adults generally favoring its color, aroma, taste, and texture to a greater extent than children and teenagers. Pinakbet, another fermented dish, demonstrated high acceptability across all age groups, particularly in terms of appearance, aroma, and taste, indicating its widespread appeal. Similarly, Binaggoongan also garnered high liking from all age groups, suggesting its universal popularity.

The significant differences in perceptions between *Pinakbet* and Golden Apple Snail Bagoong, as well as between *Binaggoongan* and Golden Apple Snail Bagoong, highlight the unique sensory profiles of each dish and the varying preferences among consumers.

Additionally, the nutritional analysis of golden apple snail bagoong revealed its moderate protein content, low-fat composition, and substantial moisture and ash content, suggesting its potential as an alternative protein source with essential mineral contributions. Finally, the observed shelf life of golden apple snail bagoong, lasting approximately three months when stored at room temperature, provides valuable insights for consumers and producers regarding its storage and consumption timelines. Overall,

the study underscores the importance of considering age-related preferences, sensory attributes, and nutritional characteristics in assessing the acceptability and potential of fermented foods like golden apple snail bagoong within diverse culinary contexts.

Recommendations

This study forwards the following recommendations based on its findings:

1. Farmers may consider propagating Golden Apple Snail for its suitability to be developed into a bagoong product.
2. Entrepreneurs may venture into developing a bagoong product made from Golden Apple Snails.
3. For further improvement and refinement of the Golden Apple Snail bagoong product, the researcher or anyone interested may seek the assistance of government agencies like the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) and the Department of Science and Technology (DOST). This shall result in a business venture.
4. Presentation of the result of the study in a research colloquium and its publication are recommended for public awareness or consumption.
5. Future research should explore other recipes where Golden Apple Snail bagoong can possibly be used.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms his steadfast commitment to upholding ethical research standards throughout the entirety of this study. Informed consent was meticulously obtained from all participants, emphasizing transparency, and honoring their autonomy. Participants were reassured of their right to withdraw from the study at any juncture, and stringent measures were implemented to safeguard their anonymity, preserving confidentiality throughout the research process. Furthermore, protocols were established to prioritize the well-being of participants, ensuring their safety and comfort remained paramount. The researcher maintained an unwavering dedication to integrity, diligently avoiding plagiarism and interpreting findings impartially to mitigate bias. It is underscored that the results obtained are solely intended to contribute to the advancement of knowledge, executed with the utmost adherence to ethical principles for the betterment of research and society as a whole.

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REFERENCES

- Beddows, C. G. (1985). Garum and salsamenta: Production and commerce in *Materia Medica*. *Yearbook of the German Archaeological Institute*, 100(1), 157-206.
- Gálvez, A. (2010). *Handbook of fermented functional foods*. CRC Press
- Hayes, K. A., Cowie, R. H., Thiengo, S. C., & Strong, E. E. (2008). Comparing apples, oranges and snails: a multidisciplinary approach to the evaluation of non-native *Pomacea* species in Asia. *Biological Invasions*, 10(1), 117-127
- Martínez-González, J. C., Jiménez-Islas, H., & Martínez-Córdova, L. R. (2019). Aquaculture of golden apple snail *Pomacea canaliculata*: a review. *Aquaculture Research*, 50(8), 2139-2152
- Monteclaro, H. M. (2019). Cultural Management and Socio-Economic Role of Small-Scale Fisheries in the Philippines. In *Fisheries and Aquaculture* (pp. 267-281). Springer
- Olympia, D. E. (1992). *Fish fermentation technology*. International Development Research Centre
- Ong, S. (2016). *Food of the Philippines*. Tuttle Publishing
- Steinkraus, K. H. (1995). Fermentations in world food processing. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 5(1), 391-444